

FEATURES OF FORMATION OF ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS-PSYCHOLOGISTS

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Abstract. *Psychological and pedagogical activity is an activity to create conditions for personal self-development, freedom of choice and creativity. The determining condition for the implementation of these goals is the awakening of subjectivity in each participant in the educational process. A significant increase in the quality of training of professionals is possible if the technological methods of education are based on reflexive methodology and an anthropological-acmeological approach. The acmeological algorithm for working with a personality includes diagnosing the subject, designing and modeling “peak achievements” and implementing acme technologies of self-development.*

Keywords: *peculiarity, formation, acmeological competence, future educational psychologists, self-development, psychological and pedagogical education.*

By acmeological literacy we understand a system of theoretical, methodological and technological knowledge of the fundamentals of acmeology, cultural and pedagogical competencies that ensure the acmeological value orientation of professional activity. The acmeological orientation of a person is a special quality of the personality of a teacher-psychologist, which is based on a set of motives and values that determine the humanistic and creative nature of professional activity, awareness of the social and personal significance of innovative transformations and responsibility for them. Acmeological culture of the individual as a component of general culture is considered by us as a personal quality that ensures the effectiveness of acme-oriented self-development, the ability to apply knowledge of acmeology in the educational space and professional activities, the formation of acmeological thinking and methods of creative activity, the desire for innovation, for success, for achieving the heights of professional excellence [6].

In this regard, the key idea in modernizing the domestic education system is the idea of self-development. For psychological and pedagogical education, this idea is of fundamental importance. Education in the modern understanding is, first of all, the creation of conditions for the development and self-development of the individual. Psychological and pedagogical activity is an activity to create conditions for personal self-development, freedom of choice and creativity. The determining condition for the implementation of these goals is the awakening of subjectivity in each participant in the educational process. A significant increase in the quality of training of professionals is possible if the technological methods of education are based on reflexive methodology and an anthropological-acmeological approach. The acmeological algorithm for working with a personality includes diagnosing the subject, designing and modeling “peak achievements” and implementing acme technologies of self-development. The professional

training of bachelors and masters should be based on purposeful work on the development of empathy, pedagogical reflection, subjective position and humanistic orientation of the individual. Reflective technologies, psychotechnics, personal growth trainings, socio-pedagogical trainings, acmeological design, business games - this is not a complete list of anthropic technologies that can provide significant assistance in solving the problem of increasing the level of acmeological culture of a teacher-psychologist [8, p. 82]. Acmeological development acts as a mandatory construct of the educational process, and its study involves an analysis of the formation and development of the need for self-realization and the ability to self-realization.

Personal development training. The purpose of the training is to develop the teacher's professional competence and develop skills for its self-development. Objectives of the training: 1. To actualize the professional potential of the teacher's personality. 2. To promote awareness of one's individual characteristics that hinder the development of professional competence. 3. Develop a personal strategy for the development of professional competence. 4. Reduce the level of rigidity and anxiety. 5. Master constructive technologies for developing professional competence. To achieve the goal of the training, psychotechnical exercises are used, the purpose of which is to promote the development of acquired knowledge and the revision of previously acquired experience. The system of exercises included in the training is aimed at creating conditions that contribute to better knowledge of oneself, awareness of one's crisis situations and ways of behavior in them, regulation of one's own emotional state, relieving anxiety, and reducing rigidity.

All this is necessary in order to timely adjust the chosen path of professional development. Introductory phase. At this stage, participants become familiar with the goals and objectives of the training, and the principles of the group's work are accepted. Participants deepen their acquaintance with each other and get to know the leader. Exercise "Everyone knows..." The entire group is divided into several microgroups (two or three people each), and each participant is given the task to prepare for five minutes and then voice a short text to introduce his neighbor in the microgroup in the following format: "Everyone knows (see, guess, think) that N..., but few people know (guess, think) that he (he has)..." For example: "Everyone knows the physics teacher, Nikolai Vasilyevich, as a very serious and responsible person, but few would think that in his free time he likes to juggle tennis balls and manages to keep up to six in the air for several minutes." Psychological commentary. This exercise is aimed at deepening the familiarity of the participants and allows you to create a positive attitude towards work. Contact phase. At this stage, a friendly, creative atmosphere is created in the group, the level of psychological defense of group members is reduced, and group norms and rules are learned.

Exercise "Compliment" The presenter invites the first participant to give a compliment to the participant on the left, he stands up, expresses gratitude and says another compliment to the next participant in the circle until everyone has spoken. Repetitions are not allowed. At the end of the exercise, the facilitator thanks everyone for their participation and work. Psychological commentary. This exercise allows you to create a favorable emotional background and a comfortable microclimate in the group. Exercise "How lucky I am in this life" Group participants are divided into pairs. The presenter offers the task: "For three minutes, tell your partner about how you are lucky in this life. After three minutes, switch roles." After the exercise there is a short exchange of impressions. Psychological commentary. The exercise is aimed at increasing the level of optimism in life, creating a good infusion of working in a group. Exercise "Professional motto"

Each group member must formulate his own motto, which reflects his professional credo, attitude towards the professional world and towards himself as a professional. 5 minutes are given to formulate the motto.

Then the group members take turns reading out their mottos and, if necessary, giving the necessary explanations. During the discussion, everyone has the right to ask each other questions and comment on their mottos. After discussing individual mottos, you can invite participants to formulate a professional motto for the group. Psychological commentary: the wording of the motto forces you to concentrate on the components of your professional orientation - what do I value in my work, what do I work for, what do I value in my profession? Finding answers to these fundamental questions helps you more clearly understand the goals of your professional life. In addition, anyone gets the opportunity to learn the professional attitudes of other group members and compare them with their own, or take someone else's motto as the basic principle of professional behavior. Exercise "Image of a teacher" Put on paper those associations that arise in relation to the teaching profession in the first column, and in the second column - associations that arise in response to the question: "What kind of teacher am I?" Write as many nouns as you can. Draw a line under the first three nouns in the first column - this is "I am an ideal teacher", do the same in the second column - this is "I am a real teacher". How much do the ideal and real images correspond to each other? What is the difference? Is it possible to be an ideal teacher? What prevents these images from coming together? Participants speak in a circle about the results of the work done.

The facilitator takes into account all opinions and draws up portraits of an ideal and real teacher, which are openly discussed and accepted by the group. Psychological commentary. The exercise is aimed at creating group cohesion, developing group work skills, awareness of barriers to professional development, and also contributes to the correction of the teacher's "I-image" and self-acceptance of training participants. Labilization phase. This stage is aimed at creating motivation for learning by making training participants aware of the ineffectiveness of their behavior patterns, behavioral stereotypes, ways of thinking, overcoming rigidity, and also at reducing anxiety. Exercise "My Strengths" The facilitator tells the group: "Each of you as a professional has strengths, what you value in yourself, what gives you a sense of inner freedom and self-confidence, which helps you withstand difficult times. When articulating your strengths, do not minimize your strengths. These qualities must be written down in the first column on the sheet. In the second column, mark those professional positive qualities that are not characteristic of you, but you want to develop in yourself." You have 5 minutes to compile the list.

Then you need to read your list and comment on it. Each person is given 2 minutes to speak. Participants can only clarify details or ask for clarification, but do not have the right to speak out. At the end, you should have a group discussion, paying attention to what was common in the statements and to the feelings that everyone experienced during the exercise. Psychological commentary. The exercise is aimed not only at identifying your own strengths, but also at helping you think positively about yourself. Therefore, when performing it, it is necessary to ensure that those participating avoid even minor statements about their shortcomings, mistakes, and weaknesses. Any attempt at self-criticism and self-condemnation must be suppressed. Exercise "Draw your career" Participants take turns drawing a curved line with a felt-tip pen on a sheet of paper, reflecting their emotional and evaluative attitude towards different stages of their professional career. If the line exceeds the zero level, it means that a positive attitude prevailed

during the corresponding period. When the line goes deeper than the reference level, it means disappointment in the profession or dissatisfaction with a particular stage of a professional career. The participant is asked to comment on his drawing by indicating which events in his professional life are associated with ups and downs in his career trajectory. Psychological commentary. The exercise is aimed at understanding the path of a professional career, as well as attitude towards certain stages of its development.

Exercise “My capabilities and limitations” Participants are asked to fill out the table. My most important achievements in the profession My barriers in the profession Psychological commentary. The exercise is aimed at understanding the achievements that have become possible thanks to the knowledge, skills and abilities within the teaching profession, as well as barriers that are caused by a lack of relevant information. Emotional self-regulation exercises. “Breathing” Participants sit in a circle. Host: “I’ll turn on some quiet music so you can relax. Please sit down comfortably. You can put your hands on your knees. Try to keep your back straight, close your eyes and breathe slowly and deeply. Breathing deeply, or even trying to consciously feel your breath, helps you relax. Now we will try one of the relaxation techniques. Counting to yourself to four, take a slow, deep breath... Hold your breath for a moment... and then slowly and calmly exhale for a count of four. Inhale... two, three, four, hold... and exhale calmly... two, three, four. Breathe like this for a minute, and you will feel yourself relaxing.... Now open your eyes, take a deep breath and exhale, look around.” “Stretching”. The feeling of anxiety “lives” in the neck below the back of the head. Let's learn how to remove it. Place your hands behind your back in a lock. Pull them, straining your back. Relax your muscles. Unclasp your hands. “Smiling” transmits nerve impulses to the emotional center of the brain. The result is a feeling of joy or relaxation. Try to smile and hold the smile for 10-15 seconds. And if you are not confident in yourself, then constantly pretend to be a confident person. If you are hunched over, straighten up, control your voice so that it does not tremble. You may be telling yourself, “I need to be confident. I will look like a confident person.” Psychological commentary. The exercises allow participants to learn to regulate their emotional state and help relieve anxiety. Exercise “I can solve problems” Participants form mini-groups to make a list of problems that arise in their professional activities. After this, there is a joint discussion of the identified problems and a generalized list is formed. Next, each participant individually evaluates on a 10-point scale the level of their capabilities in solving the identified problems in comparison with their colleagues. In this case, each participant gives two assessments - their own capabilities and the capabilities of other teachers.

Psychological commentary. The exercise allows you to realize and then evaluate your real opportunities and problems in professional development and compare them with ideal ideas. Training phase. At this stage, the psychological problem that unites the training participants is identified and realized. The motivational sphere of the individual is corrected, ways of overcoming difficulties in the development of professional competence are mastered, and the professional activity of the individual is stimulated. Exercise “My reserves” I can quickly and quite successfully increase my level of professional competence because I: know - ... can - ... own - ... have - ... It is necessary to write at least three parameters. I may be prevented from developing professional competence.... (transfer). Psychological commentary. The exercise is aimed at understanding the content of professional competence, as well as barriers to its development. At the same time, one compares one’s own results with the results of other group members and identifies general patterns in this development. Exercise “Words” Participants are offered tasks. They can be performed

collectively, but this requires appointing a team leader. Other group members will act as “idea providers.” You can also work individually. Any form is acceptable and acceptable here. The exercise consists of 3 tasks, each of which takes 1 minute. A stopwatch is used for control. Equipment: sheet of paper, pencil, stopwatch. Instructions. There are many lines (empty lines) in the column. You need to write one word on each line. All words must have two initial letters that match (for example, words starting with "holy...": fresh, free, holy, pork, etc.).

Then the results are tallied, compared with the results of the other team, unusual, original words are identified and a discussion takes place. Psychological commentary. Exercise helps overcome rigidity, reduces anxiety caused by the fear of making the wrong decision, and increases tolerance. Exercise “Composition” Equipment: sheet of paper, pencil. Instructions. You need to write a short essay on a random topic of no more than 1 page (without signing it with your name). The genre must be foreign to the group member. At the end of the exercise, the essays are read out, and the winner is the player whose authorship is not recognized by other members of the group. You are given 20 minutes to write an essay. You must write in clear, legible handwriting. After the essays are written, they are collected, demonstratively mixed and distributed to the participants. Then each participant reads out the essay given to him and identifies its author, then the group offers its opinion. As a result, the name of this person is written on this essay. At the end of the exercise, each participant is asked to take their essay and explain whether they guessed its authorship or not. Psychological commentary. The exercise is aimed at removing stereotypes of participants in the field of written speech and helps reduce rigidity of thinking. Exercise “New Opportunities”. The exercise can be performed both in group form and individually. Equipment: paper for participants, pencils, stopwatch. Instructions. You need to figure out what you can do with each of the two items whose names you will be given. How many possible options can you find? 1 minute is allotted for each subject. The total time to complete the task is 2 minutes. You need to list as many possible uses for the item as possible.

For example, a ballpoint pen. It is used for writing and drawing, but it can also be useful for other things, in particular, for making holes in a sheet of paper. Exercise “Teacher through the eyes of students” Participants are asked to assess the level of development of professional competence and behavior at work through the eyes of their students. To do this, participants need to fill out the table: My students approve of my behavior and believe that I behave competently and correctly in situations My students protest against my actions and accuse me of lack of competence in situations My students imitate my behavior After this, the results are discussed in the group. Psychological commentary. The exercise is aimed at highlighting typical situations of professional success and failure and patterns of competent behavior transmitted by students. Exercise “Locus of Control” 1. Many different events happen in our lives. We classify some events as “success”, other events we classify as “failure”, and for some events we have no reason to classify them as “success” or “failure”. Please rate each of the 10 events of “unsuccessful”, “successful” and “my real career”. If you classify an event as a “success”, then put 165 in the corresponding column with the letter “U”. If you classify an event as “failure”, then put the letter “N” in the corresponding column. If you find it difficult to classify an event as “success” or “failure,” then put the letter “O”. 2. Some people tend to believe that significant events that happen to them are the result of external forces - chance, other people, etc. Others interpret significant events as the result of their own activities, their own efforts and abilities. Please rate each of the 10 events of “unsuccessful”, “successful” and “my real career” on the following scale: 1- Very

complete agreement with the left concept 2- Almost complete agreement with the left concept 3- Some agreement with the left concept 4- Equally distant from both concepts 5- Some agreement with the right-hand concept 6- Almost complete agreement with the right-hand concept 7- Very complete agreement with the right-hand concept. Psychological commentary. The exercises are aimed at analyzing attributions of success and failure, at realizing the significance of an individual's own activity for ongoing events in all spheres of life, and most importantly, in professional activity. Exercise "What? Who? How? Where? When?" The facilitator invites each participant to make a list of desired results in the professional field and arrange it in descending order of importance or value of each. You can add to this list desires that are not directly related to your profession. Next, the presenter invites participants 166 to select a priority desire from the compiled list and create a program for achieving it based on the following rules for planning the result: • formulate the result in a positive way ("what will I have", "what will I want to have", "how will I feel" etc.); • plan only what each participant can do by himself and with himself; • the result must be represented in all sensory systems: feelings, sensations, sounds, mood, etc.; • imagine: where, when and with whom this result will be needed (mentally replaying situations in which the participant will be able to take advantage of the changes that have occurred); • think through the consequences of achieving the desired result - "what will happen if this happens?" (the result should save and preserve all the best that was before). After this, the results are discussed in the group. Psychological commentary. The exercise allows you to determine the path for further professional development. Final phase. At this stage, during a joint discussion, the results of the training are summed up and certain difficulties that arose during the training are identified.

At the end of the training, each participant can express their own opinion about the training, make their own adjustments, amendments, and innovations. Exercise "Piggy Bank" Each participant is asked to write and voice a set of techniques he has developed to help the teacher in situations of professional difficulties. Psychological commentary. The exercise is aimed at updating the experience gained during the training. Final exercise "Journey" Group participants are asked to develop a mini-project for self-development of professional competence. Each participant then develops an impromptu travel map to the land of success in developing professional competence and draws them on a piece of paper. Individual routes are presented and discussed. As a result, a general atlas of the group is compiled. Thus, the completion of the training is aimed at the teacher's understanding of the content of the process of developing professional competence. Psychological commentary. The exercise is aimed at summing up and completing the training on an emotional high. The proposed exercises allow you to see your strengths, realize your personal and professional potential; to form an attitude towards perceiving oneself in the unity of the professional "I" and the personal "I"; understand the difficulties in professional activity and ways to overcome them, as well as opportunities for further development within the profession. 8. Development of an individual trajectory of professional development. Consideration of the concepts of "career" and "trajectory of professional development". Determining possible options for teacher development in the profession. Building your own promising development profile in the profession. 9. Final diagnosis. Conducting repeated testing using a package of psychodiagnostic techniques "Study of teacher professional competence."

The program to support the development of professional competence of teachers is aimed at realizing their own potential, identifying possible ways for further professional growth and development, as well as the characteristics of teaching activities. The main emphasis is on

developing an orientation towards independence, the desire to overcome difficulties on the way to achieving a goal, increasing motivation for success, developing a tolerant attitude towards uncertainty, and reducing rigidity and anxiety. The content of the program involves both the use of traditional areas of psychological and pedagogical support (training, developmental diagnostics, psychological counseling), and developmental ones aimed at involving the teacher in active work - preparing applications for grant competitions, designing and presenting projects, preparing for participation in a professional skills competition. The presented program of psychological and pedagogical support can be adjusted and supplemented depending on the composition of participants and the conditions of the educational environment. The program of psychological and pedagogical support for the development of professional competence of teachers is designed for implementation by school teaching psychologists or specialists from psychological and pedagogical centers at regional education departments.

This understanding of acmeological development involves identifying the structural and content characteristics of its implementation (growth-development-formation-transformation) [9, p. 70]. The elective course “Acme-training for professional and personal development of students” developed by us for students - future educational psychologists includes educational and methodological materials on self-knowledge, self-development and personal self-improvement. It contains sections aimed at self-diagnosis, as well as training sessions on self-improvement and the development of professionally significant qualities. The peculiarity of the course is that it focuses on mastering a system of professional knowledge with the help of modern technologies of self-development and self-improvement: pedagogical reflection, drawing up professional and personal development programs, acmeograms, portfolios. The content of the course is aimed at creating favorable conditions for the development of acmeological culture and professional growth of a teacher-psychologist and can be implemented in the process of studying the disciplines “Professional ethics of psychological and pedagogical activities”, “Developmental psychology”, “Psychological and pedagogical anthropology”, etc. and represents the author’s vision of the problem of professional self-development of a student - a future teacher-psychologist who carries out the complex but relevant professional activity of “creating man by man” [10].

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